

**Shakhova O.O.,
Tarnavska S.I.,
Kuchuk O.O.,
Rapatskyi V.A.,
Ostapiuk Yu.R.,
Mihalko V.M.**

*Department of Pediatrics and Children's Infectious Diseases
Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072292>*

FEATURES OF CELIAC DISEASE IN CHILDREN (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract.

Celiac disease is an immune-mediated systemic disorder triggered by gluten consumption in genetically predisposed individuals. It is estimated that the global prevalence of celiac disease is around 1%. Early diagnosis is crucial for preventing long-term complications. Currently, the only effective treatment is a lifelong gluten-free diet. This review examines the epidemiology, pathogenesis, clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment of celiac disease in children.

Keywords: *celiac disease, children, gluten, transglutaminase A, intestinal biopsy, gluten-free diet.*

Objective of the study. The objective of this review is to summarize current scientific data on celiac disease in children, particularly its etiology, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, diagnostic methods, and treatment approaches. Special attention is given to the analysis of current international guidelines (ESPGHAN, ACG) and recent scientific research. This study aims to raise awareness of the latest approaches to managing children with celiac disease and improving their quality of life through timely diagnosis and effective therapy.

Materials and methods. This article is based on an analysis of foreign publications, scientific papers, and articles retrieved from sources such as PubMed and Google Scholar. Additionally, a review of contemporary international guidelines (ESPGHAN, ACG) was conducted regarding the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment of celiac disease in children.

Results and discussion. Celiac disease is a chronic disorder of the small intestine in which dietary gluten triggers inflammation of the intestinal mucosa, leading to villous atrophy and crypt hyperplasia in genetically predisposed individuals. The damage is reversible with adherence to a gluten-free diet but recurs upon gluten reintroduction [1].

Epidemiology. The estimated global prevalence of celiac disease based on population serological studies is approximately 1% [2]. According to statistical data, 60–75% of patients are female, while dermatitis herpetiformis is more common in males. The number of diagnosed cases has increased due to greater public awareness and improved serological testing; however, up to 90% of cases remain undiagnosed [3].

There is a documented rise in celiac disease incidence in Europe and the United States, particularly among women and children. This increase is likely due to environmental factors and improved case detection [4].

Children with type 1 diabetes, autoimmune thyroiditis, Down syndrome, Turner syndrome, selective

IgA deficiency, and those with first-degree relatives diagnosed with celiac disease are at higher risk of developing the condition [5].

Pathogenesis. The pathogenesis of celiac disease in children involves a complex interaction of genetic factors, immune system dysregulation, and environmental triggers (gluten consumption). Most patients carry the HLA-DQ2 (95%) or HLA-DQ8 (5%) haplotypes, which facilitate the presentation of gluten peptides to the immune system. Gluten peptides are not fully digested, leading to the formation of an immunogenic 33-mer gliadin peptide. Gliadin stimulates zonulin secretion, increasing intestinal permeability. In the mucosa, tissue transglutaminase (tTG) deamidates gliadin, enhancing its immunogenicity. Modified gliadin binds to HLA-DQ2/DQ8 on antigen-presenting cells, activating CD4+ T lymphocytes. This triggers an autoimmune response characterized by the production of antibodies against gliadin, tissue transglutaminase (anti-tTG), and endomysium (EMA). The immune-inflammatory process in the small intestine leads to villous atrophy, crypt hyperplasia, and lymphocytic infiltration (particularly CD8+ T cells) [6].

Clinical features. Celiac disease in children presents with a wide range of symptoms, from classic gastrointestinal manifestations to extraintestinal and asymptomatic forms. The clinical presentation depends on the child's age, disease duration, and the extent of intestinal mucosal damage. Symptoms typically appear in children after introducing gluten-containing complementary foods, between 4 and 24 months of age. There may be a delay or latency period between gluten exposure and symptom onset [7].

Typical symptoms include chronic diarrhea (frequent, watery, or pasty stools), abdominal bloating (meteorism), weight loss or insufficient weight gain, growth retardation and short stature, muscle hypotonia, loss of appetite, irritability, apathy, or hyperactivity [8].

Atypical (extraintestinal) symptoms are more common in children older than 3–5 years and adolescents. These include:

- Dermatological manifestations: Dermatitis herpetiformis, characterized by an itchy polymorphic rash with vesicles, predominantly on the elbows, knees, and buttocks.
- Hematological abnormalities: Iron-deficiency anemia unresponsive to iron supplementation, folate and vitamin B12 deficiency.
- Endocrine disorders: Delayed puberty, amenorrhea in adolescent girls, osteoporosis, and osteomalacia due to calcium and vitamin D deficiency.
- Neurological symptoms: Ataxia, peripheral neuropathy, attention deficit, and increased fatigue.
- Dental manifestations: Enamel hypoplasia, recurrent aphthous stomatitis (chronic mouth ulcers) [9].

Diagnosis. The diagnosis of celiac disease in children is based on a combination of clinical symptoms, serological testing, genetic studies, and histological analysis of small intestinal mucosa. Serological testing is the primary method for initial screening and includes:

- Anti-tTG IgA (tissue transglutaminase antibodies)
- EMA IgA (endomysial antibodies)
- DGP IgG (deamidated gliadin peptide antibodies)

ESPGHAN criteria (2020) allow diagnosis without biopsy if anti-tTG IgA levels are >10 times the normal range, EMA IgA is positive, and typical clinical symptoms are present [10].

Genetic testing for HLA-DQ2 and HLA-DQ8 may be used in uncertain cases or for screening relatives. The absence of these haplotypes excludes celiac disease.

Endoscopy with small intestinal biopsy is performed in cases of inconclusive serology or atypical symptoms. The Marsh classification describes histological changes:

- Marsh 0 – Normal mucosa
- Marsh I – Increased intraepithelial lymphocytes (>30/100 enterocytes)
- Marsh II – Crypt hyperplasia, increased lymphocytes
- Marsh III (A, B, C) – Villous atrophy (partial or total) [11].

Treatment. The only proven effective treatment for celiac disease is lifelong adherence to a gluten-free diet, eliminating gluten-containing products such as wheat, rye, barley, couscous, bulgur, bread, pasta, baked goods, and processed foods (e.g., sauces, sausages, and semi-finished products). The goal of dietary therapy is to achieve clinical remission and restore the intestinal mucosal structure.

Strict adherence to the diet generally leads to rapid symptom improvement, although complete mucosal healing may take time. Clinical improvements are usually noted within days. Nutritional deficiencies should be treated accordingly: iron, vitamin B12, and folic acid for anemia; calcium and vitamin D for osteoporosis [12].

Pharmacological treatment is still under investigation. Larazotide acetate, a zonulin antagonist, limits gluten passage through the permeable intestinal barrier. ALV003 (latiglutenase) breaks down gluten into

smaller fragments in the stomach before reaching the duodenum [13].

Conclusions. Celiac disease is a chronic autoimmune disorder that develops in genetically predisposed children in response to gluten consumption. It manifests in a wide range of symptoms, from gastrointestinal to extraintestinal and asymptomatic forms. Diagnosis is based on serological testing, genetic analysis, and, in some cases, small intestinal biopsy. The only effective treatment is lifelong adherence to a gluten-free diet.

References.

1. Настанова 00192. Целиакія
2. West, J.; Fleming, K.M.; Tata, L.J.; Card, T.R.; Crooks, C.J. Incidence and prevalence of celiac disease and dermatitis herpetiformis in the UK over two decades: Population-based study. *Am. J. Gastroenterol.* 2014, 109, 757–768.
3. Ravikumara, M.; Nootigattu, V.K.T.; Sandhu, B.K. Ninety percent of celiac disease is being missed. *Pediatr. Gastroenterol. Nutr.* 2007, 45, 497–499
4. King JA, Jeong J, Underwood FE, Quan J. Incidence of Celiac Disease Is Increasing Over Time: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2020;115(4):507.
5. Nellikkal SS, Hafed Y, Larson JJ, Murray JA, Absah I. High Prevalence of Celiac Disease Among Screened First-Degree Relatives. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2019;94:1807–1813. doi: 10.1016/j.mayocp.2019.03.027.
6. Caio G, Volta U, Sapone A, Leffler DA, De Giorgio R, Catassi C, Fasano A. Celiac disease: a comprehensive current review. *BMC Med.* 2019;17:142. doi: 10.1186/s12916-019-1380-z.
7. Gallegos C, Merkel R. Current Evidence in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Children With Celiac Disease. *Gastroenterol Nurs.* 2019;42:41–48. doi: 10.1097/SGA.0000000000000365.
8. Van Kalleveen MW, de Meij T, Plötz FB. Clinical spectrum of paediatric coeliac disease: a 10-year single-centre experience. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2018;177:593–602. doi: 10.1007/s00431-018-3103-4.
9. Garampazzi A, Rapa A, Mura S, Capelli A, Valori A, Boldorini R, Oderda G. Клінічна картина целиакії все ще змінюється. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.* 2007;45:611-614. doi: 10.1097/MPG.0b013e31814c3d79.
10. European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition. European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition guidelines for the diagnosis of coeliac disease. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.* 2012;54:136–160. doi: 10.1097/MPG.0b013e31821a23d0
11. Oberhuber G, Granditsch G, Vogelsang H. The histopathology of coeliac disease: time for a standardized report scheme for pathologists. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 1999;11:1185–1194. doi: 10.1097/00042737-199910000-00019.
12. Rubio-Tapia A., Hill I.D., Semrad C. et al. (2023). American College of Gastroenterology Guidelines Update: Diagnosis and Management of Celiac Disease. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2023 Jan 1; 118 (1): 59-76.

13. Leffler DA, Kelly CP, Green PH, Fedorak RN, DiMarino A, Perrow W, Rasmussen H, Wang C, Bercik P, Bachir NM, Murray JA. Larazotide acetate for persistent symptoms of celiac disease despite a gluten-free diet: a randomized controlled trial. *Gastroenterology*. 2015;148:1311–9.e6. doi: 10.1053/j.gastro.2015.02.008.